

Addition Compounds of Phosphorus Halides with Tertiary Amines

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Solid (1 : 1) and (1 : 3) addition compounds of phosphorus (III) chloride and bromide and (1 : 1) phosphorus (V) chloride and bromide with pyridine, β - and γ -picolines, quinoline, isoquinoline and piperidine have been prepared. Infrared spectra of the complexes indicate the coordination of nitrogen atom of the base to phosphorus atom in the complexes of phosphorus (III) halides while phosphorus (V) halide complexes are found to be ionic in nature.

Phosphorus (V) chloride forms complexes with ethers¹, amides² and pyridine³. Its complexes with metal halides⁴ and amides² have been shown to be ionic in nature. Phosphorus (III) chloride is also known to form addition compounds with some metal halides⁵. It reacts with primary amines with the evolution of hydrochloric acid gas⁶ and its reaction with ammonia yields a solid product which decomposes to give P_4N_6 ⁷. Addition compounds of phosphorus (III) halides with amides are reported in an earlier communication². Complexes of phosphorus (V) halides and phosphorus (III) halides with tertiary amines are not known except for one with pyridine³. Complexes of phosphorus halides with tertiary amines have been prepared and infrared spectra of these complexes have been discussed to understand their nature.

EXPERIMENTAL

Carbon tetrachloride (AnalaR) and Carbon disulphide (AnalaR) were refluxed over mercury and fractionally distilled over phosphorus (V) oxide. Petroleum ether (40–60°) was refluxed over phosphorus (V) oxide and then fractionally distilled. Tertiary nitrogen bases were purified as described earlier⁸. Phosphorus (III) chloride was repeatedly distilled in an all glass apparatus and the middle fraction was collected while phosphorus (V) chloride was sublimed before use.

Phosphorus (III) and (V) bromides were prepared by mixing phosphorus and bromine as recommended in literature⁹.

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Preparation of complexes: Phosphorus (III) chloride-3 Pyridine: To pyridine (5.0 g) dissolved in petroleum ether (20 ml) cooled to $\sim 0^\circ$, a cold solution of phosphorus (III) chloride (2.0 g) also dissolved in petroleum ether (20 ml) was added. The precipitate formed was filtered, washed with petroleum ether and dried under vacuum. A similar procedure was adopted for the preparation of complexes of phosphorus (III) chloride and bromide with other tertiary amines.

Phosphorus (III) chloride-Pyridine: To phosphorus (III) chloride (5.0 g) dissolved in petroleum ether (20 ml) at 0° , a cold solution of pyridine (2.0 g) in the same solvent (20 ml) was added. The solid product was filtered, repeatedly washed with petroleum ether and dried under vacuum. The 1 : 1 complexes of phosphorus (III) chloride and bromide with all the bases were prepared by a procedure similar to one given above.

Phosphorus (V) chloride-Pyridine: Solutions containing equimolar quantities of the reactants in carbontetrachloride were mixed to give solid products. A similar procedure was adopted for preparation of its complexes and that of phosphorus (V) bromide with other bases.

Halogens were estimated by Volhard's method¹⁰. Nitrogen was estimated by micro-analytical techniques. Conductance cell for molar conductance measurements in nitrobenzene had a cell constant 0.605. The infrared spectra of the solid adducts were recorded as paraffin mull films while liquids were examined as thin films between NaCl or KBr plates employing Perkin-Elmer-337 grating infrared spectrometer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tertiary amines react exothermally with phosphorus halides. Phosphorus (V) chloride and bromide form 1 : 1 complexes with pyridine, β and γ -picolines, quinoline, isoquinoline and piperidine (Table 1). However, phosphorus (III) chloride and bromide form 1 : 1 and 1 : 3 complexes with these amines except for quinoline and isoquinoline which form 1 : 2 complexes. The molar conductance of the $10^{-3} M$ solutions of complexes of phosphorus (V) chloride has been found to be of the order of $22-25 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1}$ which suggests that these complexes are uni-univalent electrolytes in this solvent.

Infrared spectra of the complexes from $4000-400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are given in Table 2. Tertiary amines such as pyridine are known to act as electron donors through the nitrogen atom towards electron acceptors. The strong intensity band at $3050-2950 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ spectral region due to C—H— stretching frequency in all the amines shifts to the lower spectral region in the spectra of their complexes. The spectra of 1 : 1 and 1 : 3 complexes of bases with phosphorus (III) halides are almost identical in this spectral region. The direction of shift of this absorption band is in line with that already known in the cases of the complexes of tertiary bases with a variety of acceptors^{8,11-13}.

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TABLE I

Analysis and physical complexes of phosphorus chloride and bromide with tertiary amines

Compound	Colour	m.p. (°C)	Found (%)		Calculated (%)	
			X*	N	X	N
PCl ₃ .3 Pyridine	Yellow	85 d	27.8	11.28	28.18	11.21
PCl ₃ .Pyridine	Light yellow	97 d	49.1	6.77	49.28	6.48
PCl ₃ .3β-Picoline	-do-	—	25.5	10.33	25.55	10.08
PCl ₃ .β-Picoline	-do-	—	46.0	5.81	46.2	6.07
PCl ₃ .3γ-Picoline	Orange red	65 d	24.9	10.33	25.6	10.08
PCl ₃ .γ-Picoline	-do-	72 d	45.7	5.81	46.2	6.07
PCl ₃ .2 Quinoline	-do-	72	26.7	5.27	26.9	5.02
PCl ₃ .2 Isoquinoline	-do-	78	26.5	5.27	26.9	5.02
PCl ₃ .3 Piperidine	White	145	26.9	10.33	27.1	10.70
PBr ₃ .3 Pyridine	Yellow	98 d	46.25	8.25	47.24-	8.29
PBr ₃ .Pyridine	-do-	105 d	68.3	4.00	68.57	4.06
PBr ₃ .3β-Picoline	Light yellow	—	43.1	7.17	43.24	7.34
PBr ₃ .β-Picoline	-do-	—	65.3	—	65.9	—
PBr ₃ .3γ-Picoline	Orange red	78 d	43.17	7.5	43.64	7.64
PBr ₃ .γ-picoline	-do-	89 d	65.16	3.8	65.9	3.85
PBr ₃ . 2 Quinoline	Red	108 d	45.4	7.85	45.37	7.95
PBr ₃ . 2 Isoquinoline	-do-	97 d	44.0	7.92	45.37	7.95
PBr ₃ .3 Piperidine	White	115	45.15	7.74	45.62	7.99
PCl ₅ .Pyridine	-do-	—	61.2	4.86	61.38	4.88
PCl ₅ .γ-Picoline	-do-	—	58.34	4.64	58.86	4.67
PCl ₅ .Quinoline	-do-	85 d	51.6	4.15	52.0	4.19
PCl ₅ .Piperidine	-do-	167 d	59.9	4.72	60.4	4.75
PBr ₅ .Pyridine	-do-	78 d	78.1	2.74	78.38	2.78
PBr ₅ .γ-Picoline	Yellow	81 d	75.9	2.67	76.34	2.75
PBr ₅ .Quinoline	-do-	71 d	70.98	2.5	71.4	2.64
PBr ₅ .Piperidine	-do-	173 d	70.2	2.71	71.52	2.76

* X = Halogen.

TABLE 2

Major infrared bands (cm⁻¹) of tertiary amines and their complexes with phosphorus halides

Compound	$\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{C}) + \nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	Ring vibrations	$\nu(\text{P}-\text{X})$
Pyridine (P)	1583 m, 1572 s, 1483 s	1005 s, 600 s, 405 s	—
PCl ₃ .P	1635 m, 1600 v.s, 1540 s	1010 s, 620 s, 422 m	505 s
PCl ₃ .3P	1630 m, 1605 s, 1530 s	1015 s, 625 s, 418 m	510 s
PBr ₃ .P	1635 s, 1605 s, 1540 s	1010 s, 630 s, 422 m	—
PBr ₃ .3P	1640 s, 1605 s, 1530 s	1010 m, 620 s, 425 m	—
PCl ₅ .P	1630 s, 1600 s, 1535 s	1010 m, 625 s, 425 s	625 s
PBr ₅ .P	1630 s, 1605 s, 1540 m	— — 425 m	460 s
β -picoline (β)	1610 m, 1587 s, 1492 s	1010 s, — —	—
PCl ₃ . β	1640 m, — 1562 m	1025 m, — —	510 m
PCl ₃ .3 β	1630 s, — 1550 s	1020 m, — —	505 m
γ -picoline (γ)	1595 s, 1556 s, 1490 s	— 513 s, 485 s	—
PCl ₃ . γ	1640 s, 1610 s, 1500 s	— 535 m, 490 m	515 m
PCl ₃ .3 γ	1640 s, 1615 s, 1500 s	— 535 m, 495 m	520 m
PBr ₃ . γ	1645 s, 1615 w, —	— 540 s, 500 m	—
PBr ₃ .3 γ	1640 m, 1610 m, —	— 540 m, 495 m	—
PCl ₅ . γ	1630 m, 1620 m, 1565 w,	— 530 m, 495 m	630 s
PBr ₅ . γ	1635 m, 1600 s, —	— 535 m, 495 m	465 s

Compound	$\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$	H—C—C bond	Ring vibration	H—N—C deform.
Piperidine	3290 s	1470 s, 1445 s	1120 s, 940 s, 860 m	822 s
PCl ₃ .3 Pip.	3175 s	1460 s, —	1155 s, 1050 s, 925 s	860 s
PBr ₃ .3 Pip.	3180 s	1455 s, —	1155 s, 1040 s, 925 s	865 s
PCl ₅ .Pip.	3160 s	1460 s, —	1155 s, 1050 s, 925 m	855 s
PBr ₅ .Pip.	3180 s	1460 s, —	1150 s, 1045 s, 925 s	855 s

The spectral region 1400–1600 cm⁻¹ comprises of the bands corresponding to the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of (C=C) and (C=N) of the pure amines. It is observed that these bands shift to higher spectral region in the spectra of the complexes of the bases with phosphorus halides. In the spectra of coordination complexes of these

bases with metal halides¹¹, halide alkoxides¹², carboxylates¹³ and oxyhalides¹⁴, acetylchloride⁸ and thionyl halides¹⁵, these bands have been found to shift to higher spectral region. It is significant that the frequency of the bands in 1 : 1 and 1 : 3 complexes do not differ much which indicates that the bases are similarly attached.

The ring vibrations of amines and $\nu(\text{P-Cl})$ of phosphorus (III) chloride¹⁶ occur in 650-400 cm^{-1} spectral region, while $\nu(\text{P-Br})$ of phosphorus (III) bromide¹⁶ is in a lower spectral region (390 cm^{-1}). The ring vibrations of pyridine at 600 cm^{-1} and 405 cm^{-1} shift to higher spectral region (Table 2), which confirms the coordination of amine molecules¹⁷ through nitrogen to the phosphorus halides. In the spectra of 1 : 3 complexes of amines with phosphorus (III) halides the bands which may indicate the presence of uncoordinated base molecules are absent. However, it has been observed that the bands in the case of 1 : 1 complexes are sharp while those in the case of 1 : 3 complexes are broad.

P-Cl stretching frequency of phosphorus (III) chloride at 490 cm^{-1} splits up into two bands at 510 and 475 cm^{-1} in the spectra of its complexes. $\nu(\text{P-Cl})$ of phosphorus (V) chloride¹⁶ remains unperturbed in the complexes. This may be due to the formation of ionic compounds containing PCl_4^+ as is known for pyridine complex with phosphorus (V) chloride¹⁸.

The spectra of piperidine complexes with phosphorus halides exhibit the same changes in the absorption frequencies of piperidine on complex formation as for the formation of its complexes with hydrochloric acid gas¹¹ and other strong acceptors^{12,13}. For example, the lowering of $\nu(\text{N-H})$ of piperidine in its complexes with phosphorus halides is nearly of the same order as is known for its complexes with aluminium halides¹¹, thionyl halides¹⁵ and phosphoryl halides¹⁹.

Some new bands in the spectral region 740-800 cm^{-1} which are not present in the coordination complexes of amines with other acceptors¹¹⁻¹⁵ are present in the spectra of these adducts (Table 2). These bands may be assigned to the vibrations of $\text{N} \rightarrow \text{P}$ bond. The $\nu(\text{P-N})$ single bond is known to absorb²⁰ at 980 to 1000 cm^{-1} and a coordinate bond is expected to absorb at a lower spectral region.

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